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Exploring the Kalanguya Language Primer: Proficiency Levels and Challenges in Teaching and Learning

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Abstract

Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) includes using mother tongue from pre-school to grade three. With this mother tongue, primer is embedded in teaching reading and writing. This study evaluates the challenges encountered of teachers in the utilization of Kalanguya primer in teaching reading and writing in grade 1. This study used quantitative research approach. Checklists and unstructured interviews were used as instruments to come up with data. Also, consolidated Classroom Observation Tool (COT) were averaged based on the chosen component of the COT. Data were analyzed using a Likert Scale and adjectival descriptive. The findings revealed that learners are having difficulty in learning due variations of Kalanguya language. It was found out that some terminologies in the Kalanguya primer are not applicable to all Kalanguya schools. These are needed to be contextualized and translated according to the terminologies used in the community they belong. It was also noted that learners are having difficulty in blending sounds using the Kalanguya primer.

Keywords: mother tongue, primer, mother tongue-based education, Kalanguya language, multicultural education

Introduction

This chapter discusses on the study of challenges encountered by teachers in utilization of Kalanguya Primer in Grade 1. It contains the statement of the problem that the study seeks to answer. The related concepts were also presented in detail as basis of the study.

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Background of the Study

Using mother tongue teaching in primary grades is one of the growing trends worldwide. This is evident in an increasing number of programs in education utilizing mother tongue instruction.

Philippine requires mother tongue in teaching primary grades and made it as a national policy, while some other countries permit the use of non-dominant languages in teaching. Therefore, the implementation of MTB-MLE in the Philippines serves as a model for the rest of the region (Cruz, 2015).

It was 2012 when mother tongue was implemented in the Philippines which is embedded in K to 12 Curriculum Program of Department of Education under the Memorandum Order No. 16 series 2012. This memorandum states the Guidelines about the use of Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) in teaching. This includes the mother tongue to be included as a subject and use mother tongue in teaching pre-school to grade three (Liwanag, 2017). Monje, J. et al (2019) proposed in their study that MTB-MLE policy is used to eradicate the traditional practice of leaving the mother tongue behind and give importance to the second or third language which are more dominant language.

For more than a decade into its implementation, many researches have proven its advantageous and benefits. Lorna M. Mina (2014) elaborated that the implementation of MTB-MLE of DepEd that using mother tongue in the primary grades make the learning better and faster. Learners can easily learn Filipino as the second language and English as the third language.

Consistently, using mother tongue in teaching, the performance of the learners is impressive (Ricablanca, 2014; Medilo, 2016; Namanya, 2017). Nora T. Cruz (2015) also attested in the findings of her study that the result of the performance of the learners in grade 1 manifested the effective use of the mother tongue. The learners got high result specifically on the areas on vocabulary, analysis of grammar, concept development and reading comprehension using mother tongue.

Meanwhile, Benson (2005) stressed that teaching mother tongue language schools increases active participation of parents and improves learning performance of learners. Khan, Huyamun, and Khan (2015) also stressed that using mother tongue helped learners enhanced the children's sense of belonging of the children and improved their performances in the components like affective, psychomotor and cognitive. Likewise, Sario, Guiab and Palting (2014) stated that learners are more collaborative and active as they feel the sense of belongingness when using mother tongue in teaching. Study of Vela (2015) also attested in her findings that learners' outputs are more impressive in their laboratory activities in Science subject using mother tongue as instruction. These researches compliment that the effective language for

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teaching throughout primary years of learners is their first language (UNESCO, 2008a; Ball 2009).

Along with the implementation of MTB-MLE, primer is associated with it and it was also implemented in teaching reading and writing in primary grades especially in Kindergarten and grade 1. Various researches on using primer in teaching discusses some of its benefits like the Marungko Approach. Using Marungko Approach in teaching reading and writing aid teachers in teaching in grade 1 learners easier (Laurente,2021).

However, there are concerns on teaching reading and writing in primary grades using primer as most teachers complained to that it affects the negatively the vocabulary skills and even sentence construction in English and Filipino. This is because learners apply their knowledge in Mother Tongue and prefer to use it on other subjects like English and Filipino.

Moreover, we have the problem of multilingualism in a community. There are communities in the Philippines that speak different languages because of the factors as they rooted from different indigenous group but live in one community. As a result, the children are diverse in terms of language they speak and ethnicity which they carry as they go to school and creates a diverse and multilingual classroom. Multilingualism of immigrant minority children considered by parents as an obstacle to the success of their children in school (Sierens & Stevens ,2014).

In a diverse classroom, learners have different attitude towards mother tongue that affect their performances. Lambert (1987) proposed that the attitude towards mother tongue is one of the factors that affects the performance of learners in academic attribute which is aligned to the mentalist theory. This theory constitutes the variables which are the effective, the conative, and the cognitive. This theory believes that, language can be the predictor of the behavior (Obiols, 2002; Cahapay, 2020). In this study, this theory can be applied in the attitudes of learners towards mother tongue that affects their behavior and performance in school as well.

Though some researches already proven and recommended the use of good instructional materials like storybooks to address this problem. Rudyard C. Balacano (2020) mentioned in his findings the effectiveness of storybook in Tagalog entitled "Juan Tama". It compliments that using mother tongue story books, enrich reading comprehension of the children.

Despite of various changes in teaching, reading ability is still an important ground of success in education and serves as a doorway in work achievements (Binotti, Hamilton-Gunkel, & Sipple, 2001; Gonzales, 2020).

Reading is collaborative process which consists comprehension, reasoning, and determining the correct sounds (Kamhi & Catts, 2008; Saedi, M., et al. 2016). Teaching reading to learners in kindergarten and grade 1 learners starts form focusing on letter

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sounds or phonemic awareness. Then, naming sounds of letters then blending them from the last letter sounds they learned.

Some researchers have proven the effectiveness of using movies and films teaching. Dehgani and Jowkar (2012) concluded in their study that using video texts is effective as it helps learners comprehend the lesson. Moreover, in pre-reading activities, watching videos also is good as it activates prior knowledge of the learners (Saedi, M. et al, 2016). Curriculum developers in planning and designing textbook are therefore encouraged to integrate videos and films to develop reading comprehension skills of learners.

Yousef, A. et al (2014) also indicated his study entitled "The State of Video-Based Learning: A Review and Future Perspectives" that Video-Based Learning (VBL) is conveying information in attractive and consistent way. They concluded that VBL improves learning outcomes and satisfaction.

Gonzales, J. (2020) also confirmed in her study that using video presentations on pupils occupy a noticeable positive effect on the performance of the pupils compared to the group who were given printed materials.

With these studies, inspired the researcher to conduct a study on the evaluation performance of teachers and learners on the utilization of Kalanguya Primer. This study evaluates the challenges encountered by teachers in utilization of this material and a framework that can be proposed for improvement of the primer.

Methodology/ Materials and Methods

This study is evaluation research is a combination of quantitative and qualitative method. Results were subjected to computation of weighted mean and thematic analysis. It uses more on checklists and unstructured interviews that fell under descriptive study. Ostland, et al (2015, p3.) defined it as to study and investigate circumstances that naturally happens. Macfarlane (1997) explained in her study that descriptive surveys aim to describe a special quality or trait of identified target group. It is to describe a selected participant and not necessary the whole population.

In this study, the researcher used checklists to assess the challenges of grade 1 Kalanguya teachers in Bokod and not including the whole population of teachers in the municipality. The selected teachers answered checklists incorporated with unstructured interviews.

To determine the level of teachers' performance in the utilization of the Kalanguya Blending Primer using, the COT results were consolidated computed the weighted mean.

Meanwhile, to evaluate the challenges encountered by teachers in the utilization of Kalanguya Primer, checklists were be given to the teachers to answer to collect data and subjected to assessment through a Likert Scale and computed the weighted mean.

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It also uses unstructured interviews which is subjected to thematic analysis. Thematic analysis approach is used to determine, study and interpret qualitative patterns (Villegas, 2023).

To evaluate the performance of level of the grade 1 learners in the utilization of the Kalanguya Primer, checklists were given to grade 1 teachers for them to evaluate their learners based on the competencies in the Kalanguya primer. The results were assessed through a Likert Scale and computed the weighted mean.

Population and Locale of the Study

The participants were identified according to the criteria set by the researcher to meet the objective of the study. One significant factor that was considered in selecting the participants is they are grade 1 teachers as the competencies in teaching the Kalanguya primer is mainly taught in grade 1. Another basis is they are assigned and teaching in schools using Kalanguya as primary language in teaching. The following table indicates the schools who served as participants in this study.

Table 1: Lists of Schools Using Kalanguya as Primary Language

Name of Schools	Number of Teacher (Grade 1 Teachers)	Barangay
Akbot Alicnas Elementary School	1	Pito, Bokod, Benguet
Bulo Elementary School	1	Poblacion, Bokod, Benguet
Galsa Elementary School	1	Pito, Bokod, Benguet
Pilpiok Elementary School	1	Pito, Bokod, Benguet
Palansa Elementary School	1	Bila, Bokod, Benguet
Bakian-Guiniawan Elementary School	1	Ekip, Bokod, Benguet
Line-10 Elementary School	1	Ekip Elementary School
Total		7respondents

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The Locale of the Study

The researcher conducted the study in 7 schools in the municipality of Bokod who are using Kalanguya as primary language in teaching. Akbot Alicnas Elementary School, Pilpiok Elementary School, and Galsa Elementary School were located in barangay Pito, Bokod, Benguet. Bulu Elementary School is located Poblacion, Bokod, Benguet. Palansa Elementary School is located in barangay Bila, Bokod, Benguet while Bakian-Guiniawan Elementary School and Line-10 Elementary Schools are located in the upper stream of barangay Ekip, Bokod, Benguet. The following map portrays the schools which served as respondents in this study with their respective barangay locations.

Figure 2. Administrative Map of Bokod, Benguet, Philippines Indicating the Location of Schools Using Kalanguya as Primary Language

Source: Municipal Planning and Development Office (MPDO) -LGU Bokod, (2024)

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Data Collection Instruments

The researcher used Classroom Observation Tool (COT) (Appendix L) as the main instrument to collect data to assess the performance level of the teachers in the utilization of Kalanguya Blending Primer.

But, to assess their challenges encountered in the utilization of Kalanguya primer, checklists and unstructured interviews were used as a back-up and to validate the data.

Moreover, checklists were also used as an instrument to assess the performance level of the grade 1 learners. These checklists were answered by grade 1 teachers as to how they assess their learners based on the competencies in the Kalanguya Primer.

To come up with a framework on the improvement of Kalanguya Primer, results on document analysis of the collected COT, including the findings results from the unstructured interviews and checklists results apart from the related readings were studied, analyzed and subjected to triangulation.

Data Collection Procedure

The letters of permission to conduct a study were primarily sent to the school heads of Schools in Bokod using Kalanguya as primary language in teaching. Consent forms also were distributed to the participants to comply with the Data Privacy Act. This refers to the Republic Act No. 10173, a law that aims to protect all forms of information, may it be private, personal or sensitive (National Privacy Commission 2016). Then, data collection procedure started after seeking permission from the participants and upon signifying willingness to participate on the study and subjected to collection of COTs. Checklists were also distributed to chosen 7 schools for them to answer.

Treatment of Data

The data based from the consolidated COT according to their chosen component were computed to get the average mean. Also, data from the checklists regarding the performance level of learners as were analyzed using a Likert Scale. The weighted mean was used to indicate the level of responses and treated in a 5-4-3-2-1 Likert Scale with their respective statistical limits and descriptive equivalents. In this 4-point Likert scale, the respondents were forced to commit to a certain position (Brown, 2006) even if the respondent may not have a definite opinion. The following Likert Scale is based from the Classroom Observation Tool used by Department of Education (DepEd) but with modification in terms of the given meanings (Table 2) to fully understand the meaning of the components in the COT.

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<u>NUMERICAL RATING</u>	<u>STATISTICAL RANGE</u>	<u>DESCRIPTIVE EQUIVALENCE</u>
5	4.76-5.00	Outstanding (O)
4	3.28-4.00	Very Satisfactory (VS)
3	2.56 –3.25	Satisfactory (S)
2	1.76 –2.51	Unsatisfactory (U)
1	1.00 –1.75	Poor (P)

Table 2: Descriptive Equivalence and Meaning (Used to Measure the Level of Performance of the Teachers)

Descriptive Equivalence	Meaning
Outstanding (O)	Demonstrated Level 7 in the all the three chosen components in the COT rating sheets/interobserver agreement forms.
Very Satisfactory (VS)	Demonstrated Level 6 in the all the three chosen components in the COT rating sheets/interobserver agreement forms.
Satisfactory (S)	Demonstrated Level 5 in the all the three chosen components in the COT rating sheets/interobserver agreement forms.
Unsatisfactory (U)	Demonstrated Level 4 in the all the three chosen components in the COT rating sheets/interobserver agreement forms.
Poor	Demonstrated Level 3 in all the three chosen components in COT rating sheets/interobserver agreement forms.

Moreover, to measure the performance level of the learners, Likert Scale 4-3-2-1 is used with descriptive equivalence of Outstanding (O), Very Satisfactory (VS), Satisfactory (S), and Fairly Satisfactory (FS) which is based on report cards description used by the Department of Education (DepEd).

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<u>NUMERICAL RATING</u>	<u>STATISTICAL RANGE</u>	<u>DESCRIPTIVE EQUIVALENCE</u>
4	3.28-4.00	Outstanding (O)
3	2.56 –3.25	Very Satisfactory (VS)
2	1.76 –2.51	Satisfactory (S)
1	1.00 –1.75	Fairly Satisfactory (FS)

. The following table shows descriptive equivalence and meaning as basis to measure the performance level of the learners. This is based on the School Form 9 used by DepEd but with modifications on the meaning (*Table 3*)

Table 3. Descriptive Equivalence and Meaning used to Measure the Performance Level of the Learners

<u>Descriptive Equivalence</u>	<u>Meaning</u>
Outstanding (O)	Almost all teachers answered 4 in the checklists as to how they grade their learners based on the given competencies in the Kalanguya primer.
Very Satisfactory (VS)	Less teachers answered 4 and some answered 3 in the checklists as to how they grade their learners based on the given competencies in the Kalanguya primer.
Satisfactory (S)	Most teachers answered 3 and 2 in the given checklists as to how they grade their learners based on the given competencies in the Kalanguya primer.
Fairly Satisfactory (FS)	Most teachers answered 2 and 1 in the checklists as to how they grade their learners based on the given competencies in the Kalanguya primer.

For the challenges encountered by teachers, the results based on the checklists were treated the same with the Likert Scale with the following descriptive equivalence.

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<u>NUMERICAL RATING</u>	<u>STATISTICAL RANGE</u>	<u>DESCRIPTIVE EQUIVALENCE</u>
4	3.28-4.00	Serious Problem (SP)
3	2.56 –3.25	Moderate Problem (MP)
2	1.76 –2.51	Minor Problem (MP)
1	1.00 –1.75	Not a Problem (NP)

Table 4. Descriptive Equivalence and Meaning Used to Measure the Challenges Encountered by Teachers and Learners

Descriptive Equivalence	Meaning
Serious Problem (SP)	Almost average of the teachers answered 4 in the checklists they considered the given statement as a serious problem.
Moderate Problem (MP)	Some of the teachers answered 4 and others 3 or 2 as still most them considered it as serious problem.
Minor Problem (MP)	Most of the teachers answered 3 or 2 in the checklists which it shows as a minor problem to them.
Not a Problem (NP)	Teachers answered 1 in the checklists which means it is not a problem to them.

Also, the results from the unstructured interviews were analyzed and translated for better understanding.

Finally, to come up with the framework, the data were analyzed as according to the results of the weighted mean of the checklists and also based from the teachers' suggestions during the unstructured interview apart from the related readings.

Results and Discussion

This part of the study focuses on the results and discussions, conclusions and recommendations on the utilization of Kalanguya Primer that were formulated from the data results.

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Performance Level of Teachers

This portion of results and discussion answers the first statement of the problem; What is the performance level of teachers in the utilization of Kalanguya Primer? Based from the result, the teachers manifested outstanding performance. The result from consolidated COT of seven grade 1 teachers from different schools were collected and interpreted through a Likert scale as follows.

Table 5. Performance Level of Teachers in the Utilization of Kalanguya Primers

COT Indicators	Weighted Mean	Adjectival Interpretation
Apply knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas	6.43	Outstanding
Display proficient use of Mother Tongue, Filipino and English to facilitate teaching and learning	6.71	Outstanding
Adapt and use culturally appropriate teaching strategies to address the needs of learners from indigenous group	6.71	Outstanding

This descriptive equivalence stands for 7 as outstanding, 6 as very satisfactory, 5 as satisfactory, 4 as fairly satisfactory for score of 3 and unsatisfactory for 2 and poor for score of 1 and or no stands. This scale of assessing the performance level of teachers is based on the COT as DepEd prescribed.

The indicators also are based on the selected components of Classroom Observation Tool (COT) in terms of;

- A. *Displaying proficient use of Mother Tongue, Filipino and English to facilitate teaching and learning.*
- B. *Apply knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas;*
- C. *Adapt and use culturally appropriate teaching strategies to address the needs of learners form indigenous group.*

Looking into the COT result under the three indicators reflects high in the weighted mean and outstanding as the interpretation. This means that the teachers who are using Kalanguya as the primary language in teaching are manifesting good performance level in the utilization of Kalanguya Primer in Teaching. All the three indicators in COT, they manifested high weighted mean and fell under outstanding. This manifests that they apply knowledge within and across the curriculum teaching areas and display proficient use of Mother Tongue, Filipino and English to facilitate teaching and learning. Furthermore, they also adapt and use culturally appropriate teaching strategies to address the needs of learners form indigenous group.

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This result manifested that teachers are doing well on their performance as teachers. This idea is parallel to the findings of Jemenez (2020), who said that teachers have positive attitude towards their work as based on their COT result. Lapuz (2019) also stated in their study that teachers performed very well on their rating scale on the COT. As Salazar (2022) mentioned in their study that the standardized classroom observation tool helped the teachers to reflect on their own teaching to initiate innovation for the benefit of their learners. The teacher-observer conference is a big help for the teachers to reflect on their teaching strategies and improvement. This provide the specific feedback and guidance as to instructors to allow them identify what they did well and what are points for improvements (Converse and Wenderoth, 2008). The constructive and critical feedback on their teaching methods improve their performance (Halim, et.al,2018; Munawar, et.al,2023). This COT help millennial teachers also determine the needs to be developed. LAC sessions also help teachers reflect on their teaching practices, (Eroles,2024).

As to the given indicators, application of knowledge within and across curriculum teaching areas help learners learn wider and not only to focus on one topic. All teachers aimed to improve general literacy, and this could be done through giving additional activities rather than what is embedded in the ordinary teaching in objective of the subject, Kirsten (2019).

On the other hand, the use of Mother Tongue, Filipino and English is multilingual-based education (Department of Education Order No. 74, s. 2009). The educational system supports the use of multilingual education to carry out the program of K-12 (Malone, 2022). This policy needs to prepare teachers to become effective implementers at the primary level (Bercasio, et.al.,2016).

Yadav (2024) discussed in his study that the role of mother tongue is a determinant in learning the second language like Filipino and English using different methods and classroom activities. Suggested activity could be, give the instruction in English or Filipino, and if needed, repeat them in mother tongue. It can also be giving instruction in English but try to use gestures to make it clear. Therefore, teachers must not only focus in mother tongue but also use Filipino and English.

Buduan (2023), also asserted in her research that to improve performance of learners, one strategy is to use additional textbooks in cultural language, Filipino and English. This is parallel to the third indicator which is adapt and use culturally appropriate teaching strategies to address the needs of learners from indigenous group. Teaching strategies like using contextualized materials which are familiar to the learners.

Aronson & Laughter (2015), mentioned in their study that teaching culturally relevant is helping the learners understand their own cultural beliefs and practices while exposing themselves in a wider culture. Therefore, the teaching materials to be used in teaching are primarily contextualized that reflect on their real life before it eventually moves to a wider perspective.

Challenges Encountered by Teachers

The implementation of Mother Tongue-Based education under the K-12 Curriculum made particularly in schools in Bokod where Kalanguya is used as the primary

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language in teaching, teachers encountered some challenges in the utilization of Kalanguya Primer.

This portion answers and discusses the statement of the problem; "What are the challenges encountered by teachers in the utilization of the Kalanguya Primer?" Based from the result under Statements 1-4, teachers they do have a minor problem on the utilization of Kalanguya primer. Under the statement 1, I do not have much knowledge in Kalanguya primer is not a problem to teachers. Under statement two, I do not have much knowledge on utilizing the Kalanguya Primer is minor problem to them. Under statement three, which respondents need trainings on teaching and reading using the primer appears to be a moderate problem. About their preference of using other language in teaching over Kalanguya is a moderate problem to teachers. This indicates that most of the teacher prefer using other language in teacher other than the Kalanguya primer.

The following table shows the accumulated and interpreted data from the respondents.

Table 6. Challenges Encountered by Teachers

Statements	Weighted mean	Adjectival Interpretation
1. I do not have much knowledge on the Kalanguya Primer.	28.57	Not a Problem
2. I do not have much knowledge on utilizing the Kalanguya Primer.	42.86	Minor problem
3. I need trainings on teaching reading in utilizing the Kalanguya primer.	57.14	Moderate problem
4. Preference of using other language in teaching over Kalanguya.	71.43	moderate problem

Furthermore, the result of the unstructured interviews most teachers complained that the arrangement of the alphabet in Kalanguya primer is needed to be rearranged. Most of them suggested the following;

"Mayat koma no mairingpat e arrangement nita primer. Nandugi dadan di /a/, at han /n/, /i/ han /d/. No hay unnga kat hay mapanglon daka ihapit kat / gangah ni /m/ at han gangah ni /a/, nu pan hka-dom numan kat gangah to kat /ma/. No dita Kalanguya primer kat gangah ni /a/ at han gangah ni /n/ no maittudo ni pan ka-dom day gangah to kat /an/, /an/, /an/ kanda, agpuh i gangah /n/ at han gangah /a/ hay /na.". Nalaklakan maittudo'y vowel at han consonant dadan ngay amon ingah toy /m/ at han /a/ no pan-kadom i gangah to kat /ma/ (It is better to fix the arrangement of the pimer because it on started sound /a/, /n/, /i/, and /d/. If a baby firstly speaks the consonant sound /m/ and vowel sound /a/, we blend it as /ma/. It is easier to teach consonant sounds before vowels sounds in blending just like consonant sound /m/ at han /a/)." stated Respondent 3.

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" *Mayat no maipinduwa ni hingpat arrangement nita primer tap nunta inmag me tan kat basta nansula-sulat kami ni istorya at no hipa'n letra i kadakkalan ni nauhal dima istorya kat hi-gato i napanglo ngun letra dima primer at no hipa i unhigunda ni kadakkalan i bilang to, hi-gato ngu i unhiguda'n letra dima primer. Haman i nauhal ni basehan ni nangihingpat nita primer (It is good if to re-arrange the arrangement of the letters in the primer because the time we did that is we just wrote stories and counted the frequency of the letters used in the manuscripts. The letter which si mostly used ranked as one and then the next letter is ranked as two as according to its count of frequency used in the stories. That is the basis of coming up with the primer)*" stated respondent 1.

In general, the challenges encountered by teachers in the utilization of Kalanguya Primer is more on the arrangement of the primer and a need of training on the utilization of the Kalanguya primer.

Having trainings for teachers enhance their qualities in teaching if managed well, (Yusuf, 2010). By doing so, it helps teachers improve in teaching and handling their learners. However, determine the significant effects of training programs, teachers must apply these in their actual teaching practice and provide long-term training program along with follow-up activities (Kurniawati, F. et.al, 2016).

Performance of Learners in the Utilization of Kalanguya Primer

This portion discusses and the third statement of the problem; "What is the performance level of the learners in the utilization of the Kalanguya primer based on the given competencies in the primer? The result of the consolidated responses manifested that under the competencies, identifying the sounds of the letter, reading the sound of the letter and identifying and writing the upper-and-lower case of the letter is interpreted to be outstanding. It is interpreted in the table below.

Table 7: Performance Level of the Learners Based from the Competencies in the Kalanguya Primer

Competencies	Weighted mean	Interpretation	Evans, M. et al. (2006) stated in their study that acquiring knowledge in letter sounds is
1. Identify the sound of letter.	3.57	Outstanding	
2. Read the sound of letter	3.57	Outstanding	
3. Identify and write upper- and lower-case letter.	3.29	Outstanding	
4. Blend the sound of letter on letters previously learned.	2.57	Fairly Satisfactory	

easier in vowels and for letter with consonant-vowel names. Moreover, in teaching letter names and sounds, Levin, I. et al. (2005) revealed in their study that learners easily learn

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on letter names rather than letter sounds. The learners could only speak the letter sounds if they could name it. Therefore, some teachers use possible remedy like pictures and letter sound cards. McNamara, G. (2012) attested in the result of his study that using pictures and letter sound cards in teaching letter sounds is effective.

Moving forward into blending the sound of letters, the result is low and fell under fairly satisfactory. This means that this competency must be given attention to improve their performances.

Connor and Padeliadu (2000) attested in their study that learners who lack sufficient knowledge of the letter sounds have difficulty in blending consonant vowel consonant (CVC) words to four and five letter words. There is a need to review the letter sounds then blending syllables and blending of words.

Challenges Encountered by Learners

This portion answers the statement of the problem 4; "What are challenges encountered by the learners in the utilization of Kalanguya primer? The result shows challenges is more on the variations of Kalanguya language. The following table shows the result of data gathered.

Table 8. Challenges Encountered by Learners

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Adjectival Interpretation
1. Some terminologies used in the primer are not applicable in all Kalanguya schools due to variations of Kalanguya language.	57.14	Serious problem
2. The learners have less knowledge on Kalanguya language.	42.86	Moderate problem
3. The learners prefer using other dominant language than Kalanguya as their mother tongue.	42.86	Moderate problem
4. The learners were taught at home with other dominant language rather than Kalanguya.	42.86	Moderate problem
5. Utilizing the Kalanguya Primer in teaching negatively affects learners' performance in other subjects like Filipino and English.	42.86	Moderate problem

Result shows that learners are having serious problem because terminologies used in the primer are not applicable in all Kalanguya schools. Among the seven 7

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respondents, four (4) of them answered serious problem which got a weighted mean of 57.14%. This means that most of the schools who are using Kalanguya as primary language is having difficulty on learning due to various language used in the school. According to the Kalanguya Orthography, revised 2017, Kalanguya language has four (4) varieties. This is parallel to the result of the study that learners are experiencing difficulty for having different languages in school as it fell under a serious problem.

Moreover, the result shows that learners have less knowledge on Kalanguya language. The result weighted average interprets it as moderate problem as some teachers answered 4 in the checklists. Also, the learners' preference of using other dominant language than Kalanguya as their mother tongue appears to be a moderate problem. This means that some of the learners prefer using other dominant language rather than Kalanguya which is their mother tongue. This is aligned to statement number 4 wherein the learners were taught at home with other dominant language and it falls under moderate problem. Lastly, utilizing the Kalanguya Primer in negatively affect learners' performance in other subjects like Filipino and English as the result falls under moderate and minor problem with the same weighted mean of 42.86%.

Generally, these results manifest that learners are really having difficulty in learning due to the use of Kalanguya Primer in teaching due to some factors like the use of various language in school and use of dominant language other than Kalanguya.

Sierens and Avermaet (2014) mentioned in their study that having large number of home languages present in schools seen as hindrance to effective acquisition of the majority or dominant language. This is connected on the common phenomenon, Foreign Language Anxiety (FLA). This pertains to learners' distress because they experience difficulty to be themselves and connect with other people because of their limited knowledge on the new language (Horwitz 2017; Bensalem and Thompson 2020). Along with this, there learners are belonging to bilingual and multilingual group. Bilinguals are those in the process of learning first foreign language while multilinguals are those have learned more than one language (Thompson and Khawaja, 2026). A study conducted by Bensalem and Thompson, (2020) revealed that bilingual learners manifest less self-confidence than multilingual learners. Meanwhile, to assess the challenges of learners in the utilization of the Kalanguya Primer, the result manifests a serious problem in terms of the effectivity of terminologies used if it is applicable in all Kalanguya schools. Due to variations of Kalanguya language appears to be a serious problem as shown in the table below.

This means that this material should be contextualized to schools who are using different Kalanguya terminologies other than what is already written in the primer.

Reyes, (2019) affirmed that contextualization is a way to provide learners a learning environment where they can relate and learn meaningfully. Instructional materials in schools written in Filipino and English is better also if translated in the local language where learners can understand, (Sumalinog, 2019). The significance of localization and contextualization in teaching has meaningful impact to education (Bello, et, al., 2023).

Proposed Framework

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A framework that can be proposed for the utilization of Kalanguya primer is inclusion of the 4 Kalanguya varieties which are Kib-al, Dë-key, Ni-ni and Kal-ing. Terminologies are needed to be contextualized to be applicable in the particular schools using Kalanguya as primary language.

It is also needed to modify the arrangement of the letters in the primer for easier learning and blending of the sounds.

The following flow chart shows the proposed framework for the points for improvement of the primer.

Figure 3. Framework for Improving the Kalanguya Primer

Summary

This evaluation research on the utilization of Kalanguya primer was gathered through collection of COT results, checklists and unstructured interviews were studied and analyzed. The summary results were arranged as follows.

1. The findings revealed that performance level of teachers in the utilization of Kalanguya primer is outstanding based from the result of consolidated COT forms that were analyzed through a Likert Scale and computed average mean. This manifested that teachers are applying the chosen in their teaching which are;
 - A. *Displaying proficient use of Mother Tongue, Filipino and English to facilitate teaching and learning.*
 - B. *Apply knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas;*
 - C. *Adapt and use culturally appropriate teaching strategies to address the needs of learners from indigenous group.*
2. The challenges encountered by teachers in the utilization of Kalanguya Primer is

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more on the arrangement of the primer which the teachers suggested to be rearranged and modify for better teaching reading. Also, teachers needed a training on the utilization of the Kalanguya primer.

3. The performance level of learners according to competencies in the Kalanguya primer revealed that are having difficulty on blending sounds of letter on the letters previously learned as the result fell under fairly satisfactory.
4. The challenges encountered by learners is more on the variations of Kalanguya language which negatively affect there learning which led to misunderstandings of the terminologies and lesson. Contextualization of terms is needed with the consideration of the 4 Kalanguya varieties which are Kib-al, Dë-key, Ni-ni and Kal-ing.
5. A framework that can be proposed for the utilization of Kalanguya primer is inclusion of the 4 Kalanguya varieties which are Kib-al, Dë-key, Ni-ni and Kal-ing. Terminologies are needed to be contextualized to be applicable in the particular schools using Kalanguya as primary language. Also, the modification of arrangement of the letters in the primer for easier learning and blending of the sounds.

Conclusions

With the objective evaluating the utilization of the Kalanguya primer, the following conclusions were drawn.

1. The teachers' performance on the utilization of Kalanguya based from the consolidated results of the COT, teachers manifested outstanding performance within the three indicators. This indicates that they apply knowledge within and across the curriculum teaching areas, display proficient use of Mother Tongue, Filipino and English to facilitate teaching and learning. Applying knowledge within and across curriculum teaching areas is likely to be integration of language and content though giving of additional tasks to learners which does not only focus on the subject specific language (Kirsten, 2019). According to Robin Fogarty (1991), curriculum integration is helping learners provide valuable connections while learning. This could be through provision of interdisciplinary topics which are arranged around overlapping concepts. For instance, language teachers might select the concepts in literature concept of Heroes to teach particular parts of speech.

Furthermore, the result manifest that the teachers highly adapt and use culturally appropriate teaching strategies to address the needs of learners form indigenous group. This is teaching using culturally appropriate materials. These materials refer to learning resources which have local contents (Begi, 2014). Using instructional materials like textbooks, pictures, charts and flashcards which are culturally-relevant is a great aid to teachers in meaningful learning (Shankar, 1980; Begi, 2014). Also, they display proficient use of Mother Tongue, Filipino and English. Using mother tongue also is a way of preservation and imparting indigenous education to learners. It is a tool of imparting and preserving culture from generation to generation.

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Therefore, teachers manifested that they apply in their teachings the chosen components in the COT.

2. For the challenges encountered by teachers, it turns out that it is more on the arrangement of the letters in the primer. The result manifested that teachers are having difficulty in teaching the primer due to that arrangement of the letters. Result also revealed that teachers need a training on the utilization of the Kalanguya Primer while their concern about having knowledge on the primer is not a problem. Also, in the utilization of the Kalanguya primer appeared to be minor problem.

It is recommended to have a training for teachers and fix or modify the arrangement of letters in the primer for easier teaching and learning letter and blending sounds.

3. Moreover, the result of performance level of learners, the result turns out that under the competencies, in identifying the letter sounds, writing the upper and lower case of the letter is easier for the learners to learn. They got fell under outstanding adjectival interpretation. However, on the competency, blending letter sounds to the previous letter sounds learned, their performance level is fairly satisfactory which means the learners are having difficulty under this competency. Therefore, teachers must give attention and efforts on teaching blending letters sounds.

Teachers need to have trainings on teaching reading and blending sounds using the primer. It is necessary for them to be able to teach well using the primer.

4. In assessing the challenges encountered by the learners in the utilization of the Kalanguya primer reflected that some terminologies are not applicable to all school using Kalanguya primer as primary language due to Kalanguya variations. As said earlier, Kalanguya language has four (4) varieties which are Dë-key, Kib-al, Ni-ni and Kal-ing (Kalanguya Orthography, revised 2017). Therefore, the terminologies must be contextualized and translated along with the terminologies used in the particular community. This contextualization is doorway to provide learning environment where learners can relate (Reyes, 2019).

On the other hand, some learners have less knowledge on Kalanguya language as reflected in the result of the study. This means that teachers must prepare give more instructional materials that is written in Kalanguya language. As said by Shankar (1980) and Begi (2014), in their studies that instructional materials like textbooks, pictures, charts and flashcards which are relevant to the culture and language of the learners, provide a meaningful learning environment.

In conclusion, the result of the study showed that most of the challenges of learners in the utilization of the Kalanguya primer are the variations of Kalanguya used by the learners and the multi-language they used in the school. Terminologies in the Kalanguya need to be contextualized to be aligned on the terminologies used by the learners on the particular communities.

5. To come up with the proposes framework, the consolidated data from related readings, checklists weighted mean result and consolidated COT forms and

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unstructured interviews were studied and analyzed.

To improve the primer, it is better if we consider the 4 varieties in Kalanguya in polishing the primer and contextualize the terminologies that is appropriate to the learners' language. It is also good if the letters in the alphabet be re-arrange for easier learning and understanding.

Generally, the outstanding performance of teachers did not reflect on the performance of learners. The reason behind is these are not comparable and parallel. The performance of the teachers is based on COT components while the learners are based on the primer components. The teachers' challenges are on the arrangement of the letters in the primer which is hard for the learner to blend. While the learners' challenges are on the variations of Kalanguya language. Hence teachers need trainings on the utilization of the primer specially on blending sounds. Also, there is a need to re-arrange the letters in the primer as suggested by the teachers. All these are needed for the proposed improvement of the Kalanguya primer.

Recommendations

While this research presents the level of performance of teachers and learners and their challenges in the utilization of the Kalanguya primer, the researcher would like to recommend the following;

1. Performance level of teachers is outstanding or high based from the result of the study. However, the COT components that were focused to are;
 - A. *Displaying proficient use of Mother Tongue, Filipino and English to facilitate teaching and learning.*
 - B. *Apply knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas;*
 - C. *Adapt and use culturally appropriate teaching strategies to address the needs of learners from indigenous group.*

It is better to include all the given components in the COT to assess the performance of the teachers.

2. Teachers' challenges result revealed that is more on the arrangement of the primer that is needed to be re-arranged. Hence, there is a need for teachers to help each other on fixing the arrangement of the primer. Teachers also needed a training on the utilization of the primer.
3. The performance level of learners in some competency like identifying the letter sound and wiring the upper and lower case of the letter is outstanding. However, the competency blending the letter sounds to the previous learned letter sounds fell under fairly satisfactory. This means that the competency on blending sounds is the competency needed to be addressed. It is recommended to have trainings of teaching blending sounds using the primer.
4. The learners' challenges are mostly on the variations of Kalanguya language. The terminologies used are not applicable in all schools using Kalanguya as primary language. It is then recommended that the terminologies should be contextualized by the teachers in a particular area based on the Kalanguya terminologies on where they are teaching. They may seek the help of elders in that particular community.

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5. The proposed framework for the improvement of the Kalanguya primer is on the inclusion of the 4 varieties of Kalanguya which are Kib-al, Dë-key, Ni-ni and Kal-ing. Terminologies are needed to be contextualized as according to the language used by the learners in the particular community. The arrangement of the letters in the primer is also needed to be modified and re-arranged. However, teachers in this context are the most important participants when doing this modification or re-arrangement.

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